

Matters and Strategies of Educational Policies in Open and Distance Learning Mode of Education: An assessment of National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN)

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Abstract

Background: This paper examines the evolution and stages of Nigeria's National Policy on Education (NPE), emphasizing its role in promoting education as a tool for human socialization, skill development, and value transmission across generations.

Method: The study reviews the NPE as a framework for achieving sustainable educational system development in Nigeria, analyzing its historical focus on conventional education and its challenges in addressing sectoral deficiencies.

Findings/Results: The paper identifies significant challenges in the formulation and implementation of educational policies, highlighting their limited success in resolving persistent educational issues. It also underscores the NPE's innovative strategies, which led to the establishment of the National Open University of Nigeria as a dedicated Open and Distance Learning institution.

Implications: The NPE serves as a critical channel for fostering sustainable educational development, offering guidelines that support innovative educational models like open and distance learning.

Conclusion: The National Policy on Education provides a foundation for sustainable educational growth in Nigeria by introducing innovative strategies that address educational challenges and promote inclusive learning systems.

Recommendations: Policymakers should address implementation challenges by refining strategies and ensuring adequate resources to support innovative educational models, such as open and distance learning, for broader impact.

Introduction

Governments, stakeholders and other partakers of educational growth and development are often considered to be the main drivers and movers of the wheel of teaching and learning programmes at all levels in the society. It is generally accepted that the impact of education as a structure and or tool for socialization, innovation, adding creative value, growth and evolution of the society cannot be over emphasized. Studies have shown that education is amongst the most essential ways to develop human qualities, create capacities, eliminate limits, and, in the end, expand the range of accessible chances and alternatives for long-term well-being. Also, human beings are to educate and to be educated; in addition, the prime goal of education is to sustain individual and societal improvement. This process contains both tangible and moral dimensions, hence the educational programs and policies play pivotal roles in these social and individual progresses (Genelza, 2022; Odusany, 2019).

As a way of buttressing the viability of education toward societal growth and development, Osokoya (1987) maintain that education is a distinctive way in which the society inducts its young ones into full membership. Education is a tool for human socialization and impartation of innovative skills and developmental values from generation to generation. Be it as it may, available evidences have shown a constant dwindling in the standard of education, its development and growth in Nigeria. The study of Luise (2023), support the fact that functional education is a fundamental tool for societal development and growth, and yet Nigeria's education system is in a state of disrepair, which is impeding the country's growth and

development. The study further explained that the development of education in Nigeria has been backward for several reasons.

Arguably, the success and or otherwise of the educational systems largely depend on their ability to formulate, implement, guide and administer, assess as well as uphold viable strategies and policies. These policies then act as guide to the system, as well as rules and measures that would enhance growth in the educational system in particular and the society at large. In other words, a successful society needs an educational policy to guide it in the process of such initiation. Policies therefore become the process that brings certain principles or ideas into practice. It is taken to be any course of action . . . relating to the selection of goals, the definition of values or the allocation of resources' (Ward, Bagley, Lumby, Hamilton, Woods, & Roberts, 2016). Hence, when policy is applied to education; it becomes a standard tool that guides stakeholders in education in navigating educational sector.

Educational policies, like any other societal phenomenon, are not static rather dynamic. They are formulated and reviewed to reflect with time, goals, needs, vision and mission of the stakeholders. According to Awokoya (1981), since the first edition in 1977; the 2nd and 3rd editions of educational policies were published in 1981 and 1998, they are implemented to keep up with the dynamics of social change and the demands on education. This 4th edition was necessitated by some policy innovations and modifications, and the need to update the 3rd edition (1998) accordingly. In fact, the basis advancement and change associated with the 4th edition of NPE include the reintroduction and lifting of ban order on Open and Distance Learning (ODL) mode of educational programme by the government of Nigeria.

ODL refers to a flexible and inclusive approach to learning that allows individuals to access education without traditional entry requirement and study remotely from any location. It combine the principles of openness which provides inclusive access to educational opportunities for all learner, distance education, which enables students to study at their own pace and convenience through various remote learning methods and technologies. It also aimed at widen access to ensure equity

and equality of opportunities to university education and also promotes education for all and lifelong learning opportunities. In Nigeria, National Open University of Nigeria is the only mono-mode Open and Distance Learning University operating in the country today (NOUN, 2018).

Ogunbayo (2013) maintain that ODL within the Nigeria experience encourages physical attendance of tutorials in addition to academic counseling services made available as compliments for tutorial sessions. To foster interaction between learners, in certain cases online support is offered through real time chat and email discussion groups with staff and students. In Nigeria, ODL has however become grounded and remains an alien system of inculcating knowledge to students, who are not accustomed to conventional universities. Nevertheless, and in spite of these progresses, there is still the myth that the Nigerian education circle still struggles with the perception of distance learning.

The poor performance of the education sector and the inability of existing Nigerian universities to accommodate teeming population of students applying for admission in Nigeria have become very worrisome. Okoroma (2016) queried: What is the problem? Is the educational policy faulty or is it the implementation that is faulty? What are the implications for national development? It is based on this premise that this study investigates the issues and strategies of educational policy on the open and distance learning mode of education in Nigeria through the review of scholarly literature and studies.

Conceptual framework

Concept of ODL

The concept of ODL has become a house hold name in education sector nowadays. According to online definition, ODL is any learning activities within formal, informal, and non-formal domains that are facilitated by information and communication technologies to lessen distance, both physically and psychologically, and to increase interactivity and communication among learners, learning sources, and facilitators.

In a general term, Open and Distance Learning is typically contrasted with 'conventional' or 'face-to-face' mode of education. The later may be described as the form of education which takes place in classrooms. The rationale for distance education from its earliest days has been to open opportunities for learners to study regardless of geographical, socio-economic or other constraints. The use of the term Open is intended to highlight the feature of the theory and practice of distance education (Opara-Onukwugha & Chikwendu 2015).

In addition, distance education is any educational process in which all or most of the teaching is conducted by someone removed in space/or time from the learner, with the effect that all or most of the communication between teachers and learners is through an artificial medium, electronic or print. By definition, in distance education, the normal or principal means of communication is through technology. However, teachers in conventional classrooms may use technology as a supplement to their teaching, but it is not their principal means of communication (UNESCO, 2001a). Also Ministry of Education (2015) maintain that it is a system of learning and teaching that is grounded in the principles of open and resource-based learning and takes place in different contexts at a multiplicity of sites, through a variety of mechanisms and learning and teaching approaches.

Concept of Educational Policy

Delving into the meaning of educational policy may be difficult to comprehend without understanding what policy is. In a nutshell, a policy according to Dora (2015) is an official commitment of the authority to the vision, mission, principles, goals and objectives expressed in a document which an organisation adopts for a given area and strategically intends to implement. Collins online Dictionary defines policy as a set of ideas or plans that is used as a basis for making decisions, especially in politics, economics, or business. By implication, a policy is a stated intent and usually implemented by an organisation via certain procedures. Besides, policies can support in both subjective and objective decision making.

Education: Education is considered fundamental for achieving full human potential, developing an equitable and just society, and promoting national development. It

is a spiritual pursuit, development of innate human potentialities and social orientation of human beings. Hence, education can be referred to as a holistic development of the individual and the societal potentials. According to Adesemowo and Olufumilayo (2022), education deals with the total process of human learning by which knowledge is imparted, faculties are trained and different skills are developed. Education is also defined as the act or process of educating or applying discipline on the mind or a process of character training.

Government and other stakeholders in education are more concerned with the development of workable guideline for educational advancement at all level that would bring all time societal development. Generally, education Policy lays particular emphasis on the development of the creative potential of each individual. It is based on the principle that education must develop not only cognitive capacities -both the 'foundational capacities' of literacy and numeracy and 'higher-order' cognitive capacities, such as critical thinking and problem solving - but also social, ethical, and emotional capacities and dispositions (National Education Policy, 2020).

Educational policies are initiatives mostly by governments that determine the direction of an educational system (Okoroma, 2000). According to Awokoya (1981), educational policy is directed towards increasing the quality of life of a people. He believes that the objective of any policy is to satisfy individual needs, community pressures and the degree of complexity and sophistication to which socialized personnel must be educated and trained to meet these demands. Educational policy is a statement that contains the principles, rules and regulation that govern education decisions that are crucial to the realization of educational goals

History of National Education Policy in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the philosophical foundation for basic education is placed on The National Policy on Education (NPE) as revised in 2013. It emphasizes the universal right to education, protected under Nigeria's Child Rights Act 2003 and the Compulsory, Free Universal Basic Education Act of 2004. Historically, educational

policy in Nigeria has passed through two significant stages --- the colonial and the post independent era and these have been phases of education and in educational development across Africa.

Scholars have contended that before the advent of the Europeans African indigenous education was quite adequate in so far it met the requirements of the society at the time (Ociti, 1973; Marah, 2006). Scanlon (1964: 3) also argued that “the education of the Africans before the coming of the European was an education that prepared him for his responsibilities as an adult in his home, his village and his tribe.” During the colonial era, Western form of education was introduced by the colonialists. Lugard (1965) pointed out that the main purpose of Western education was to produce clerks and interpreters to aid the administrative machinery of the imperial overlords.

On attainment of political independence, the colonial education system was inherited by Nigeria and this was criticised for being too theoretical to be able to make meaningful impact on the life of Nigerians (Akinlua, 2007). For instance; Subjects taught in schools reflected the taste of the colonial education officials; hence school curricula were built around the existing colonial values. Unfortunately, the same problem which informed dependency on past colonial education relics seems to have continued till date. Woolman (2001: 41) remarked that “African school systems today still follow the rigid structure of time periods and grade-level progression found in Western education.” Also, it is doubtful if this colonial education heritage has been discarded since for Akinlua (2009: 3) issues such as models of learning and teaching were still based on the European system and structure.

However, within the first two decades of Nigeria’s independence, the education system and policy were characterised by series of committees and conferences. Concrete steps toward curriculum reforms started in 1966 by the National Education Research Council (NERC) under Chief Awokoya (Sofolahan: 1987). In September, 1969 the curriculum reform conference was held with discussions on appropriate curriculum contents and problems in Nigeria. Further conferences in 1973 led to the production of the National Policy on Education in 1977, 1981 and

2004. The production of this document and the eventual take-off of the policy in 1982 in some states of the country, marked the end of the post-independence piece-meal and rather disjointed adjustments to the colonial education heritage bequeathed on Nigeria.

Scholars maintain that since the publication of the first edition in 1977; the 2nd and 3rd editions were published in 1981 and 1998 respectively in keeping with the dynamics of social change and the demands on education. This 4th edition was necessitated by some policy innovations and changes, and the need to update the 3rd edition (1998) accordingly. These innovations and changes include: The lifting of the suspension order on Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programme by Government (Okoma, 2006; Awokoya, 1981).

In furtherance, Year 2004, ushered in the 4th National policy on education which is based on a dynamic model of formulating educational policies that is adaptive to change and most appropriate for developing countries which specifies on adult education, non-formal education, specific- education type and open and distance learning (ODL). The open and distance learning aspects of these policies provides opportunities for those who are unable to complete their regular channels, hence prepare them for useful living in the society, along the lines of strictly guided international standards.

Open education though not new in Nigeria has been given much prominence of recent; it is becoming a notable access to basic and tertiary education for Nigerians. Open and distance learning (ODL) within this new context for Nigerians not only shares the goals of conventional education, but it also aim at providing access to historically under-served, place bound and highly motivated population.

As on record, in the West Africa, the National Open University of Nigeria of Nigeria (NOUN) is the first full-fledged university that operates in an exclusively open and distance learning mode of education. According to Osikomaiya, (2018) one of the objectives of establishing ODL is to ensure the provision of quality education for functional, cost effective and flexible learning that adds lifelong and willingness to learn. ODL was established in Nigerian in 1983 and later suspended, but

resuscitated in 2002 which was a laudable achievement towards making education accessible and affordable to all without age limit or geo-graphical and towards achieving the millennium development goals.

The increase in quest for knowledge, a growing demand for higher education, coupled with interest to make education accessible and affordable to all and high level of ICT usage contributed huge success towards ODL operations in Nigeria. NOUN focuses mainly on open and distance learning system, which is more typically of conventional universities in Nigeria and other parts of the world. Its constant academic renewal and relevance and the dynamics of globalization it projects, plus the introduction of information and communications technologies (ICT), resulted in a tidal.

Wave of information that has in many cases, overwhelmed the Nigerian educational sector in the last few decades and this has resulted in radical changes in the educational needs of individual and society at large to meet the changes of the 21st century. The attendant lack of required capacity by our tertiary institutions, noticed as a result, has brought to the fore, as a viable and readily-available option the issue of open and distance learning as an innovative and cost effective approach to the educational process. The ODL offers structured learning in which instructors and students are separated by time and space, making use of materials such as print materials, audio and video cassettes, CD ROMs, television and radio broadcasts, as well as multimedia components such as computers and satellite transmission (Imam, 2012).

Despite the seemingly pluses of ODL, the issues affecting education system in Nigeria are still obvious. For instance, the study of Okoroma (2016) centred on the poor performance of the education sector in Nigeria which has become very worrisome. This study based on questions on; What is the problem? Is the educational policy faulty or is it the implementation that is faulty? What are the implications for national development? The findings blame the distortions in the educational system on the ineffective implementation engendered primarily by lack of political will, lack of continuity of programs, and corruption. The situation has

hindered national development and, until urgent action is taken to review Nigeria's educational system, its national aspirations will continue to be compromised.

Educational policies are initiatives mostly by governments that determine the direction of an educational system. In the view of Awokoya (1981), educational policy is directed towards increasing the quality of life of a people. He believes that the objective of any policy is to satisfy individual needs, community pressures and the degree of complexity and sophistication to which socialized personnel must be educated and trained to meet these demands. The following considerations, according to Awokoya (1981), are necessary to guide the formulation of adequate educational policy.

- It should be formulated and adopted through a political process which acknowledges the reality and legitimacy of conflicting interests and desires among its participants
- It should portray some elements of guidance for properly directed and coordinated action towards the attainment of the desired goals
- It should contain information on the broad objectives that should be reached
- It should be a binding guide on the actions of those implementing it
- It should be enforceable and enforced by the society which formulates it.

A study by Mahesha, Niranjana and Rajeshwari (2024) concerning the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in India reveals several implications on Open Distance Learning (ODL). It pointed out that one of the primary goals of the NEP 2020 is to increase access to education for all, regardless of their geographic location or socioeconomic background. And one of the key implications of NEP 2020 on ODL is the emphasis on digital technology. Another important implication of NEP 2020 on ODL is the focus on flexibility and customization. The policy recognizes that every learner has unique needs and learning styles, and therefore, education should be designed to cater to the individual needs.

The policy encourages the development of robust quality assurance mechanisms for ODL programs to ensure that they meet the same standards as traditional classroom-based programs. The study concludes that implementing innovative

assessment methods and strategies tailored for Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs has a significant impact on the accuracy, authenticity, and validity of assessing and evaluating learning outcomes. It also highlights the potential for enhancing the overall quality of ODL education by incorporating innovative assessment approaches. In conclusion, the study advised the educators and administrators in ODL programs to consider implementing these strategies to improve the assessment process and promote better learning outcomes for students.

In their review, Biswas and Ghos (2016), discusses the challenges and strategies for assessment in open and distance learning (ODL) in India. It was argued by the authors that assessment in ODL is complex and requires a flexible approach that considers the unique characteristics of ODL environments. Also, Chawla (2017) reviews the literature on assessment in ODL in India. The author asserts that assessment in ODL is a complex and evolving field, and that there is a need for more research on the topic. Further study by Dwivedi and Kumar (2018) present a case study of assessment of learning outcomes in IGNOU, India's largest ODL institution. The authors maintain that IGNOU has made significant progress in assessment of learning outcomes, but that there is still room for improvement.

Challenges of Policy of Education formulation and implication as it apply to ODL

The gaps between policy formulation and implementation arouse investigations to identify factors that constrain impactful formulation and effective implementation of educational policies in Nigeria and its implications on ODL mode of education. Benson, Obichere, Eweama and Eke (2021) in their analysis of the challenges to implementation of ODL programmes in tertiary institutions in developing countries highlighted the following as the main factors; dearth of well-defined national distance education policies, dearth of trained cadre of professionals to support the implementation of the policies and programmes of distance education; technological constraints, dearth of collaborative partners, low level of funding in Nigerian educational institutions and erratic power supply among others.

UNESCO (1997), maintain that in developing countries there are some common barriers to the effective implementation of open and distance learning. Lack of funding, problems of allocation of resources and sustained support are perhaps the most important ones, having detrimental effects on quality and achievement. Another problem is lack of human resources with sufficient competence and motivation. The third major problem is technological infrastructure, which prevents the effective use of appropriate technologies. Finally, lack of strategic planning and coordination as well as varying donor perceptions and interests may reduce the level of achievement.

Chigbu and Kolubowei (2019) in their study on the challenge to the realization of policy implementation in Nigeria education sector, highlight some factors that are responsible to include the following:

- Lack of political stability
- Corrupt practices;
- Inadequate funding
- Political interference
- Insufficient human and materials resources
- Lack of continuity

There is always a gap between the planners and policy implementers: In Nigeria, for instance, there has been a wide gap between educational planners and policy makers, the executors or implementers of the various educational policies. To buttress this, a study carried out by Oyeromi, Akinkuowo, and Kareem (2014) further explain that the planners have not always been involved at the planning stage and this had in no small measure affected the implementation of such plans and policies adversely. In a situation where educational administrators, teaching staff, and other school personnel have no say in the policy making process and on the policy that finally emerges, the implementation of such a policy is likely to be problematic.

In the history of educational planning, agencies do not give adequate consideration to involve the implementers of such plans and policies. This has been hampering

successful implementation of educational plans and policies. Other factors include; political factor, frequent change of policies, misplacement of priority as well as lack of monitoring, supervision and evaluation system

Other studies have pointed out the factors contributing to the failure in formulation and implementation of Educational Policies. Olukoya, . Bowale, and Okunlola (2018) narrated some of the constrains as follows:

1. **The nature of Nigeria's philosophy of education:** This has to do with the attitude of formulating and implementing seemingly not working regulations aimed at supporting educational policy. It is argued that any education system that is devoid of a philosophy would lack a sense of purpose and direction (Yakuba, 2020).
2. **Issue of Policy on language:** The Government appreciates the importance of language as a means of promoting social interaction and national cohesion and preserving cultures but the inability of Educational policy to identify and codify varieties of Nigerian English (literary, written or spoken) as well as mother tongues has become an issue of concerned (Amuseghan, 2010).
3. **Unstable and frequent changes in educational policies:** According to Odukoya (2006) constant Changes in Policies tend to negatively affect the implementation of the National Policy on Education and consequently the standard of education. Each of the Presidents, Ministers, Governors and Commissioners had their own different conceptions and policies on education that they tried to implement during their tenure.
4. **The process involved in policy formulation as opposed to its implementation** Furthermore, it is one thing to succeed in getting research findings translated into national policies; it is another ballgame altogether getting them implemented. This may often necessitate further follow-up and intensive lobbying. Part of the problem here has to do with incessant changes in government and paucity of technocrats within the government. Lack of understanding of the power of well-formulated policy and diligent implementation in effecting educational and national development apparently account for this (Olukoya, . Bowale, & Okunlola. 2018),

5. **Initiating effective supervisory approach:** Chigbu and Kolubowei (2019), maintain that autonomy or free hands should be given to the supervisors and monitoring team of the policy process to carry out their statutory responsibilities without imposing negative intuition by political juggernauts.
6. **Brain drains of qualified lectures/scholars:** Over the past decades now, there has been a massive exodus of brilliant and most talented lecturers and scholars to other sectors of the economy and outside the shore of the country in search of greener pasture (Yaro et al., 2015).
7. **Lack of political will to implement educational policies:** Ugwuanyi and Chukwuemeka (2013) argue that there is the need for a conscious effort by government leadership to reduce the extent to which politics infiltrate bureaucratic activities in Nigeria.

Strategies to improve ODL mode through Police on Education

Several investigations and studies have revealed the possibilities or prospects towards improving ODL mode of education by means of formulation and implementation of appropriate and concise policy on education, UNESCO (1997) highlighted the important strategies for future development of ODL education to include; harmonization of goals, policy clarification and coordination at national level, as well as regional coordination and collaboration. Capacity building is important, including increased professionalism in planning and management of open and distance learning systems. Other aspects are networking between national stakeholders, better integration between education and training systems and the productive sector, and progressive autonomy and capacity for continuing operation after aid has ceased.

UNESCO (1997) further states that the education community cannot ignore the revolutionary changes brought about by technological developments and infrastructure now shaping the new information society. Present political and commercial interest in and commitment to the reinforcement of a world-wide electronic communication infrastructure (Internet, information superhighways, World Wide Web, etc.) should be of great interest to education, and particularly to open and distance learning (UNESCO, 1997).

Olukoya,. Bowale and Okunlola (2018), suggested the following as strategies for improving ODL mode of education thus: first establish a standard for conducting research [research method] and for reporting - from problem identification, title formulation, proposal writing, sampling, instrument development and validation, fieldwork, data analysis, result presentation, abstract writing and referencing. Second, institute an annual specialized seminar/training session on the significance and process of policy formulation and implementation for researchers and for key government functionaries. Third, institute an annual specialized training on effective advocacy and lobbying strategies (same audience) Evolve research themes that have strong bearing on the formulation and implementation of national educational policies. Forth, budget adequately for these seminars/training programmes and for the necessary logistics to follow-up and follow-through on getting our research findings adopted for policy formulation and implementation.

Agabi (1999) sees educational planning strategies as viable way to improving ODL education. He further stated that decision making process toward actualizing a specific goal of education while systematic process of realizing future educational development need and goals of the society is termed educational planning. Chigbu and Kolubowei (2019) listed parts of strategies to enhance ODL through educational policies as follows:

- Understanding the relevance of educational policies create avenue for continuity
- Delegating professional without interference
- Allocation of resources
- Delegating supervisory Team

Conclusion

Education creates and adds values to individuals and societal development and growth. It provides an avenue for individuals' intellectual and skill advancement. However, successful educational programmes may depend on some factors including a well-articulated policy. The role of educational policy is to provide a

guideline and or roadmap to a coherence and sustainable educational system that could yield remarkable growth and development of the society. On the other hand, the introduction of Open and Distance Learning (ODL) mode of education in Nigeria may seem to have come to fill in the gap of the deficiencies that exit in current educational system as well as the demand for flexible learning opportunities that enhance greater participation in educational programmes.

Through educational policy the government and other stakeholders in educational sector can achieve the educational goals. For instance; the educational policy of the government gave birth to the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) as an ODL mode of education in Nigeria. It may be argued that ODL; through its various programmes and mode could provide succor to the lingering poor educational performance and wider coverage of teaching and learning, Several steps and measures, including licensing of private owned Universities, have been taken by the government and other stakeholders in educational sector aimed to improve the ODL educational system. Hence, the formulation and implementation of well-articulated policies on education enhances the ODL mode of education.

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